

Methodology for Application Of a Research Approach In the Academic Training Of Student Teachers

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Abstract

In contemporary academic education, a new approach to examining and understanding scientific problems is being introduced. An approach based on methodological pluralism, interdisciplinarity, and globality. It relies on active and interactive learning. This scientific-practical approach, which rejects imperativeness and supports research discovery, is called the research approach. The article discusses the technology for its application in the overall teaching process of the academic discipline. The process of this technology is formed by several methodological forms reflecting the activity, operational, and reflexive stages. Self-reflective formats such as "pedagogical essay," pedagogical case analysis, and pedagogical narrative are included in the technology. Project-based activities are also utilized. Working on various pedagogical projects develops students' professional skills. The article presents an empirical study reflecting the quality of the tools and the development of students' skills. The empirical data express the change in students' skills, attitudes, and relationships in various professional environments and contexts.

Keywords: Competence, Problem, Cooperation, Education.

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1. Introduction

1.1 The research approach as a concept in academic learning

The problem of applying a research approach in education is not unfamiliar in the field of pedagogical sciences. In various aspects, it has been referred to as active, creative (Doncheva, Y., 2020) [1]; leads to an understanding of the essence of phenomena and processes (Kenderov, P., 2017) [2]; represents plans and procedures for investigation that encompass steps from broad assumptions to detailed methods, data collection, analysis, and interpretation (The Selection of a Research Approach) and others. Today, this idea has practical implications for innovative, multi paradigm education. In contemporary teaching methodology, there has long been a tendency to transition from strictly scientific-theoretical knowledge to its applicability and practical significance. Or in other words: a transition from one paradigmatic stage to the next. If until recently the educational paradigm was primarily oriented towards personal development, today the multi paradigm model is evolving on how to develop motivation and primarily how to organize an environment in which students manage their full participation. In terms of the research learning environment, it can be argued that motivation is "a conscious need and the ultimate result carries psychological value" (Sulichka, I., 2019) [3]. In this sense, participants in the educational process must reach a point where they are ready to make truly deep methodological and technological changes for themselves as subjects in the educational process. It is precisely in the context of academic-teacher metamorphosis that the research approach is justified as leading in contemporary multi paradigm academic education. It is considered an innovative approach, in line with contemporary understandings of the scientific community for the development of creativity and competencies in the field of teaching and learning. It can be said that its main characteristics are: innovativeness and reflexivity, which are conceptualized through the maxim "learning through development for all".

The research approach in teaching directs each student to pursue their own path for constructing and organizing their knowledge; it rationalizes the idea that it is more important for the student to know how to learn than to memorize information. It is an active approach to learning and teaching,

assuming independent choice of learning direction.

Students develop knowledge and understanding of scientific ideas, as well as an understanding of how researchers investigate the problem (Burnhamand, A., 2002) [4]. The aim of the research approach is to organize and provide such a learning environment in which students scientifically explore specific aspects of pedagogical issues. Thinking of the research approach as a primary direction, as a kind of viewpoint in teaching practice (Kozhuharova, G., 2015) [5], outlines it as an innovative, complex, professionally reflective approach. By applying the research approach, new interdisciplinary connections are actualized or created; new contextual interactions reflecting innovative processes in education, new methodologies, and teaching practices are established. Its focus on research encompasses a comprehensive reorientation of teaching practice towards the concept of developing thinking in the learning process, and thus a reorientation of education through a holistic new culture that will enter school education.

An important scientific-pragmatic dimension in the research approach is to set research tasks close to students' interests and cognitive abilities. It is believed that students have a certain level of social and civic competence, but due to the specificity of the pedagogical profession, they must develop and enhance their skills for successful professional realization. Therefore, one of the scientific-pragmatic dimensions of the research approach is the creation of effective strategies and technologies for forming competencies that are the basis for successful professional realization. The specificity of the research approach, applied to students' activities, is expressed not so much in the amount of knowledge they acquire, but in the understanding and application of operational methods for cognitive activities.

The methodological-pragmatic dimension of the research approach outlines the leading role of the teacher. They construct and select methodological tools and shape the research orientation. The teacher's methodological culture and their ability for methodological reflection play an important role: the ability to analyze their own scientific activity, scientifically justify, critically

understand, and creatively apply certain concepts, forms, and methods of knowledge.

The application of the research approach to the teaching process delineates flexibility and adaptability to the issues discussed in the academic environment. This does not mean replacing or skipping study topics and exercises. It means a change in interpretation to enhance interest and motivation towards working on the particular issues. It is important to emphasize that what may be a significant problem in one group does not always prove to be significant in another. In this sense, the choice of the problem is not as important as its formulation to be understandable to everyone. The research approach is based on the foundation of "studying" the problem - all students participate in the discussion, conduct experiments, ask questions, raise hypotheses, gather and present arguments for one or another thesis. In this way, they independently "discover" the facts and the connections between them. Therefore, it can be argued that the application of the research approach is at the core of the modern concept of academic teaching and is conceptualized as forming the multi paradigm methodology in the process of academic education.

2. Research Reflective Technology in Training Student Teachers

It can be argued that there flective research technology is theoretically based on Grow, G.'s (1991) [6] activity model for developing learning motivation. In the first level, students are fully dependent, and the teacher assumes the role of a coach. They use various motivational techniques to develop interest, organize an interactive and dialogical learning environment, so that students are engaged in the learning process, provoked to explore pedagogical issues, and even their life experiences. Along their own cognitive development path, students discover various problems, specific questions arise regarding a particular project. At this stage, the teacher's role changes to that of a "motivator". The transition is made to the stage of "interested". Here, students become acquainted with the scientific foundations of the academic discipline on a pragmatic level, as well as with the technology through which they acquire their knowledge – the freedom of academic knowledge, the choice of means and

methods, pedagogically reasoned personal opinion. At this level,

the first public academic presentation of the product of the educational project is realized – thematic presentation (1). Students develop self-management and skills to achieve learning goals. Different personality types, learning styles are outlined, confidence in skills is built. This stage is directly related to the students' value system, as during the academic public presentation, they express their life and pedagogical values, connecting what they learn with their future goals in a reasoned manner. The planned educational activity in the next steps is linked to the "involved" level. Here, they work in teams - writing and mutually reviewing pedagogical argumentative essays (2). Trust is built among the students working in teams. In this model of educational activity, research learning is strongly manifested, as students themselves research the problem – they seek sources, read various materials provided by the teachers. Their self-assessment and ability to work with others, learn from them and with them, are developed and deepened. Developing these skills is a pedagogically oriented process directly related to planning the next educational activities - working with pedagogical cases and pedagogical interpretation of didactic visualization (3). These educational activities are linked to the "self-managing" level, and the role of the teacher is "delegating". Resources are provided to the students - films, images, case studies, which they pedagogically interpret and solve. Placed in this expert role, responsibility towards learning and teaching as a holistic subject-subject process is fostered in them. At this level, teachers work with many additional resources, send new articles or educational news to students; they maintain interactive communication with them for comments, suggestions, opinions. Very often at this level, stimulated by the teacher, students present their productive strategies to the academic audience. At this level, the self-reflection questionnaire for self-assessment and self-realization (4) is also conducted during the course. It is here that self/reflection is most pronounced. Personal reflection is expressed in self-awareness and a "mental perspective" directed towards oneself, towards one's activities and actions. Personal reflection is associated with an analysis of one's own "Self" (Changalova, V., 2013) [7]; reflection on one's qualities and habits (Atanasova, M., Stavreva, I., 2008) [8]. A

characteristic feature of the comprehensive reflective technology for training students is its scientific-pragmatic orientation. The construction of educational activities in the presented manner is not a random choice by the teacher. It has a deeply motivational and regulatory character: the student presents verbally - develops pedagogical speech and masters presentation to an audience (1); the student presents in writing - presents a culture of written pedagogical speech and literacy (2); the student pedagogically analyzes didactic visualizations and case studies (3) - assumes roles and seeks pedagogical solutions; the student develops self-reflective skills when working with the questionnaire (4).

3. Empirical Verification of Reflexive Research Technology

The aim of this empirical study is to trace whether there is a change in students' activity when applying a research-reflexive approach in the teaching process. The study examines the educational-research materials of 845 students studying the academic discipline "Elementary School Pedagogy". During the execution of the first project - preparing a presentation on a pedagogical topic (1), the statistical data show relatively low values. This result outlines about 29% - 35% of educational-research products that meet the set criteria. Within this range, skills for active learning and application of proactive strategies are outlined. Tracking the data in subsequent educational-research activities throughout the period shows an upward development of skills, attitudes, and attitudes towards the educational-research form of training. The empirical data on criteria for the research instrument "pedagogical essay" (2) present the development of research reflections among students. The pedagogical essay as a form of assessment carries its subjective factor. To minimize it, empirical criteria have been introduced, outlining the substantive, linguistic, and technical essence of the task. The criteria do not have a formative character regarding the overall shaping of the research student status with which the teacher works. With the change in the form of educational-research activity, minimal change is outlined - within the range of 32% - 37% in meeting the criteria. It is precisely this minimal upward change in empirical data that provides a basis for deepening teacher reflection. Passing through the lowest level - oral

presentation, the next: written presentation, teacher reflection constructs the third level in reflexive technology. It is associated with the intellectual and praxeological level within the pedagogical content. Students are given the opportunity to solve a pedagogical case (3). The purpose of this empirical study is to track whether there is a change in the activity of students when applying a research-reflexive approach in the teaching process. The study examines the educational research materials of 845 students studying the academic discipline "Elementary School Pedagogy." When performing the first project - preparing a presentation on a pedagogical topic (1), the statistical data present relatively low values. This result outlines around 29% - 35% of educational research products that meet the specified criteria. Within this range, skills for active learning and the application of proactive strategies are outlined. Tracking the data in the subsequent educational research activities throughout the period shows a rising development of skills, attitudes, and attitudes toward the educational-research form of learning. The empirical data on the criteria for the research instrument "pedagogical essay" (2) present the development of research reflections in students.

The pedagogical essay as a form of assessment carries its subjective factor. To minimize it, empirical criteria have been introduced, outlining the substantive, linguistic, and technical essence of the task. The criteria do not have a formative character regarding the overall formation of the research student status with which the teacher works. Changing the form of educational-research activity outlines a minimal change - within the range of 32% - 37% in meeting the criteria. It is precisely this minimal ascending change in the empirical data that provides a basis for deepening teacher reflection. Passing through the lowest level - oral presentation, the next: written presentation, teacher reflection constructs the third level in reflexive technology. It is related to the intellectual and praxeological level within the pedagogical content. Students are given the opportunity to solve a pedagogical case (3). The empirical data on case work outline relatively high indicators compared to the initial empirical data. Boundaries between 29% - 52% are outlined in which students develop their skills. The empirical data processing presents a situation of smooth and moderate transition from oral speech (through educational presentations), written speech (through pedagogical essays) to simulation

gaming activity within educational research activities. These relatively high ascending results are directly related to the research reflection of the teacher. The specificity of working with cases outlines not only the need for knowledge, skills, and attitudes. It requires their application in a research-constructed pedagogical environment.

A reflexive variant in technology is for the pedagogical case to be transformed into a pedagogical interpretation of didactic visualization. This transformation is aimed at pedagogical analysis of an image from a lesson, classroom, or other pedagogical fragments. Here, the pedagogical reflection of the teacher aims to create a research-pragmatic environment for developing research and pedagogical skills in students.

In the criterion-empirical presentation of educational research activities in elementary school pedagogy, empirical data from the research instrument "self-reflective questionnaire" (4) should be included. It serves as a self-reflective assessment of the research technology of education, one's own achievements, and self-assessment within the framework of reflexive research technology. The empirical data show changed skills, attitudes, and student teacher reflections in a positive aspect. They outline a change in student reflections and a striving for intellectual assessment growth - 70% - 77.87% responded positively and self-assessingly.

Statistical data from the empirical results of research instruments allow for a graphical representation of the quality of reflexive research technology in training student teachers. It outlines the overall statistical image of the intellectual, pragmatic, and self/reflective growth of students within the range of 29.11% - 77.87%.

Figure 1. Statistical Measurements of Reflexive-Research Technology

Source: Author.

4. Conclusions and Generalizations

The research approach is a scientifically pragmatic, interactive approach conceptualized through a shift in paradigmatic orientations in higher education. The research approach shapes inquiry-based learning. At the same time, it is shaped by inquiry-based learning and conceptualized through its characteristics. The article assumes that the application of a research approach transforms the learning process into a process of inquiry-based learning. Its subjective characteristics develop as reflective-inquiry learning and reflective-inquiry teaching.

Reflective-inquiry technology is considered as an activity-oriented structure, linked to the goals of education. It reflects on the quality and effectiveness in the process of education. A characteristic feature of the overall research technology for student education is its orientation towards teacher self-reflection. The designed educational activities are directed towards pedagogical axiology, understanding freedom as responsibility towards oneself and others. An important aspect in the planned activities is the orientation towards students' personalities and skills. The design of educational activities in the presented manner is not a random choice by the teacher. It has a deeply motivational and regulatory character. Operationally, the reflective-inquiry technology has an algorithmic and activity essence, realized through its technological components - project/theme, pedagogical essay, case.

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